

PRODUCTION EFFICIENCIES OF BRINJAL IN AKOLA DISTRICT

Nikita W. More, Sandip S. Thakare and Samir S. Lande

Agricultural Economics and Statistics Section

Shri Shivaji Agriculture College, Amravati, Maharashtra, India.

(MS Received: 05.02.2024; MS Revised:07.03.2024; MS Accepted:08.03.2024)

MS 3189

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS AND STATISTICS.)

Abstract:

In this study an attempt has been made to study the economic analysis of selected rabi vegetables in Akola District. The present study was based on primary data. For the present study, 120 vegetable growers were selected from Barshitakali, Patur and Balapur tahsils of Akola district. From each tahsil five villages were selected randomly and eight vegetable growers from each village were selected by multistage random sampling technique. The study showed that the Per hectare cost of cultivation at cost C_3 of brinjal, tomato and chilli were Rs. 148319.02, Rs. 160100.79 and Rs. 140719.62, respectively. The input-output ratio at cost C_3 for brinjal, tomato and chilli growers were 1.47, 1.44 and 1.29, respectively. The mean level of technical efficiency, economic efficiency and allocative efficiency has been estimated at 92.88 per cent, 81.52 per cent and 87.43 per cent in brinjal cultivation. In tomato cultivation, it has been estimated at 96.81 per cent, 90.79 per cent, and 91.13 per cent. And in chilli cultivation, it has been estimated at 93.91 per cent, 81.96 per cent and 86.98 per cent, respectively.

Keywords: Allocative efficiency, Brinjal, Cost, Economic efficiency, Technical efficiency

Introduction:

The potential of vegetables to contribute to the national economy has been well recognized in recent years. India is the second-largest producer of vegetables, next only to China. Total horticulture production in 2022–23 is estimated at a record 351.92 million tons, which is an increase of about 4.74 million tons (1.37%) over that achieved in 2021–22. (pib.gov.in website)

Brinjal (*Solanum melongena L.*) is one of the most commonly grown vegetable crops of the country. In the year 2022, area of brinjal in India was 744 thousand ha and production were 12768 million tons. (Statista website) And in Maharashtra the area were 20.85 thousand ha and production is 361.79 million tons and in Akola district area of brinjal 428ha and production 15500 metric ton. West Bengal is the largest producer of brinjal in India.

Materials and Method:

Collection of data: Data for the present study was collected from the Akola district. The multistage random sampling was used for collection of data and data pertains for the year 2022-2023. For the present study, Akola district was selected purposively. From Akola district, three tahsils was selected on the basis of potential area of brinjal.

Selection of villages

List of vegetable growing villages was obtained from Taluka Agriculture Office of the selected tahsil and 5 villages from each tahsil was selected randomly. Eight farmers from each village were selected for study.

Selection of cultivators

The list of vegetable growers along with the area under brinjal was obtained from revenue authority of the selected villages. 40 growers for Brinjal was selected from 15 Villages.

Cost concepts

Details of standard cost concept to be used for working out per hectare cost of cultivation and returns are as under.

Cost concepts: This includes cost A_1 , A_2 , B_1 , B_2 , C_1 , C_2 and C_3 .

Cost A_1 = All actual expenses in cash and kind incurred in production by the producer. The following items are included in cost A_1

- 1) Wages of hired human labour.
- 2) Wages of permanent labour.
- 3) Wages of contract labour.
- 4) Wages of hired bullock labour.
- 5) Imputed value of owned bullock labour.
- 6) Charges of hired Machinery.
- 7) Imputed value of owned machinery.
- 8) Actual rate of manures and fertilizer.
- 9) Actual rate of seed.
- 10) Imputed value of owned seed.
- 11) Imputed value of manure.
- 12) Actual value of pesticides, herbicides, hormones, etc.
- 13) Irrigation charges.
- 14) Land revenue, cesses and other tax.

15) Depreciation on farm machinery, implements, equipment Farm buildings, Irrigation structures, etc.

16) Interest on working capital.

17) Miscellaneous expenses.

Cost A_2 = Cost A_1 + Rent paid for leased in land

Cost B_1 = Cost A_1 + Interest on value of owned capital assets (excluding land)

Cost B_2 = Cost B_1 + Rental value of owned land (net land revenue) less land revenue + Rent paid for leased in land.

Cost C_1 = Cost B_1 + Imputed value of family labour.

Cost C_2 = Cost B_2 + Imputed value of family labour.

Cost C_3 = Cost C_2 + 10 per cent of Cost C_2 on account of managerial functions performed by farmers.

Gross income = Value of main produce + Value of by produce.

Farm business income = Gross returns - Cost ' A_1 '

Family labour income = Gross returns - Cost ' C_1 '

Net income = Gross returns - Cost ' C_2 '

Cost of production per quintal

Cost of production per quintal of selected vegetables has been worked out by total cost minus value of by produce dividing by main product in quintal.

Input Output Ratio

The probability crop production cannot be justified completely unless input output ratio were worked out. This is the ratio which represents returns obtained per rupee investment. It was worked out by dividing gross return by the total cost. It was calculated at Cost A_1 , Cost A_2 , Cost B_1 , Cost B_2 , Cost C_1 , Cost C_2 , and Cost C_3 .

Output-input ratio at Cost A_1 = Gross income / Cost A_1

Output-input ratio at Cost A_2 = Gross income / Cost A_2

Output-input ratio at Cost B_1 = Gross income / Cost B_1

Output-input ratio at Cost B_2 = Gross income / Cost B_2

Output-input ratio at Cost C_1 = Gross income / Cost C_1

Output-input ratio at Cost C_2 = Gross income / Cost C_2

Output-input ratio at Cost C_3 = Gross income / Cost C_3

Technical and Allocative Efficiency

In the present study stochastic production frontier function and stochastic frontier profit functions were used to determine the farm-specific technical and economic efficiencies respectively.

Stochastic production frontier function-

In the present study, the stochastic frontier approach was used to measure the farm specific efficiencies of rabi vegetables crop. (Aigner et al., 1977; Kalirajan and Shand, 1889; Sharma and Datta, 1997) The stochastic frontier model is called a 'composed' model because the error term is composed of two independent elements, namely-

$$\Sigma_i = v_i - u_i \quad i = 1, \dots, n$$

The term v_i is the symmetric component and permits random variation in output due to factors like weather and plant disease. It is assumed to be identically and independently distributed $v_i \approx N(0,$

σ^2v). A one-sided component ($u_i \geq 0$) reflects technical efficiency relative to stochastic frontier $Q_i = Q(X_i, \beta) e^{v_i}$. Thus $u_i = 0$ for any farm lying on the frontier while $u_i > 0$ for any farm lying below the frontier. Hence expression (u_i) represents the amount by which the frontier exceeds realized output. The distribution of u_i is assumed to be half-normal.

A measure of technical efficiency was first introduced by Farrell (1957) for a cross-section of firms by using a deterministic approach. He illustrated his ideas of efficiency using a simple example involving firms that use two inputs (x_1 and x_2) to produce a single output (q), under the assumption of constant returns to scale. The curve SS' in following figure represents the unit isoquant of fully efficient firms and permits the measurement of technical efficiency. If a given firm uses quantities of inputs, defined by the point P, to produce a unit of output, the technical inefficiency of that firm is represented by the distance QP, which is the amount in which all inputs could be proportionately reduced without a reduction in output. This is usually expressed in percentage terms by the ratio QP/OP, which represented the percentage in which all inputs can be optimally reduced to achieve technically efficient production. Hence, the technical efficiency (TE) of a firm can be measured by the ratio $TE = OQ/OP$

Technical inefficiency is equal to $1 - OQ/OP$ and takes a value between zero and one. Hence, it provides an indicator of the degree of technical inefficiency of the firm. A value of one implies that the firm is fully technically efficient.

Specification of the model

$$\ln Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + (V_i - U_i)$$

Where,

Y_i = Output of Selected crop (Quintals/ha)

X_1 = Human labour (days/ha)

X_2 = Machine hours (hrs/ha)

X_3 = Quantity of seeds (kg/ha)

X_4 = Quantity of fertilizers (kg/ha)

V_i = Random variable

U_i = Farm specific technical efficiency related variable

β_0 = Intercept/Constant

Stochastic profit frontier function

Table 1 Per hectare input utilization of selected brinjal growers

Sr. No	Particulars	Unit	Size of land holding			
			Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Hired human labour					
	a) Male	Days	33.25	35.08	44.41	36.50
	b) Female	Days	76.87	112.75	105.87	93.09
	Total		110.12	147.83	150.29	129.59
2	Bullock Labour	Pair	7.17	8.18	8.37	7.72
3	Machine charges	Hrs.	6.00	7.50	10.58	7.52
4	Manures	Carts	9.62	17.16	27.58	16.00

Stochastic frontier profit function was used to estimate economic efficiency of selected vegetables. (Ali and Flinn, 1989; Rahman, 2003; Galawat and Yabe, 2012). The stochastic profit frontier function was estimated as-

$$\Pi_i = f(X_i, P_i) + (v_i - u_i)$$

where,

Π_i = Normalized profit at cost-A of the i^{th} farmer.

X_i = The vector of variable input prices divided by output price faced by the i^{th} farm.

P_i = The vector of fixed factor of the i^{th} farm.

V_i = random error due to factors outside the control of the farmers.

U_i = A non- negative random variable associated with economic inefficiency component

The economic efficiency in relation to the stochastic profit frontier is given by,

$$EE_i = \exp(-u_i)$$

Specification of the model

$$\ln \Pi_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + (V_i - U_i)$$

Where,

Π_i = Normalized profit at Cost-A of the i^{th} farmer.

X_1 = Human labour wage rate per hr normalized by output price of i^{th} farm.

X_2 = Machine wage rate per hour normalized by output price of i^{th} farm.

X_3 = Price of seed per kg normalized by the output price of i^{th} farm.

X_4 = Price of fertilizer per kg normalized by the output price of i^{th} farm

V_i = Random variable

U_i = Farm-specific economic efficiency related variable

β_0 = Intercept

Factor price is obtained by dividing the price of input with the output price. Allocative efficiency was estimated by dividing economic efficiency with technical efficiency for each farm.

$$AE_i = EE_i / TE_i$$

Constraints in production and marketing

The constraints in production and marketing of selected vegetables was analysed by using Garrett's ranking technique. The ranks given by each respondent was converted into per cent position by using the formula:

$$Per\ cent\ position = \frac{100 \times (R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given to i^{th} constraint by the j^{th} individual and

N_j = Number of constraints ranked by the j^{th} individual.

The mean score values estimated for each factor was arranged in the descending order. The constraints with the highest mean value were considered as the most important one and the other followed in that order.

Results And Discussion

Per hectare input utilization of selected brinjal growers

It is seen from Table 1 that per hectare hired human labour utilization was observed to be highest in large group i.e.,150.29 days, and at overall level, it is 129.59 labour days. Female labour was required more as compared to male labour. Overall bullock labour utilization was 7.72 pair days.

5	Irrigation	No.	34.75	36.83	37.25	35.89
6	Fertilizers					
	N	Kg	92.62	103.16	89.00	94.35
	P	Kg	47.62	46.16	48.37	47.44
	K	Kg	25.00	40.91	39.37	32.57
	Total		165.25	190.25	176.75	174.37
7	Seed	Kg	0.80	0.85	0.81	0.82
8	Plant protection chemicals	Liter	3.73	2.85	3.48	3.45
9	Family human labour					
	a) Male	Days	35.75	38.25	31.70	35.36
	b) Female	Days	51.50	53.66	60.75	54.35
	Total		85.50	91.91	92.45	88.84

At the overall level, utilization of seed was 0.82 kg per hectare. The farmers in the large size group used more amount of manure i.e., 27.58 and at overall it was 16.00 carts per hectare. Inputs were efficiently used in brinjal cultivation; hence, hypothesis is accepted.

Per hectare cost of cultivation of Brinjal

It could be seen from Table 2 that the per hectare total cost of cultivation of brinjal at the overall level for the sample as a whole was Rs. 148319.02 amongst the different items of expenditure. Overall, human labour accounted for 32.45 per cent share in the total cost cultivation and it was the highest of all items included in the cost of cultivation. The share of the rental value of land was 24.47 per cent to the total cost.

The proportion of other items of expenditure, such as bullock labour (2.67 per cent), machinery charges (1.91 per cent), seeds (10.98 per cent), manure (3.21 per cent), and fertilizer (1.66 per cent), had a share of interest on working capital and fixed capital was (1.63 per cent) and (2.51 per cent), respectively. The total cost of cultivation (Cost C₃) of brinjal was highest in the large size group, i.e., Rs.160678.53 per hectare, followed by medium size group Rs.156477.81 and small size group Rs.138059.24 per hectare, respectively. At overall level per hector cost 'A₁' was Rs.83928.03 and B₁ and B₂ were Rs.87659.49 and Rs.123964.36, respectively, which was 59.10 per cent and 83.57 per cent of total Cost 'C₃'.

Table 2: Per hectare cost of cultivation of Brinjal

(Rs/ha)

Sr. No	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Hired human labour				
	Male	9975.04 (7.22)	10525.01 (6.72)	13325.12 (8.29)	10950.05 (6.58)
	Female	15375.30 (11.13)	22550.23 (14.41)	21175.67 (13.17)	18619.12 (11.5)
2	Bullock Labour	3687.50 (2.67)	4416.67 (2.82)	4187.50 (2.60)	3994.79 (2.67)
3	Machine Labour	2700.04 (1.95)	3000.14 (1.91)	3025.42 (1.88)	2856.41 (1.91)
4	Seed	16050.33 (11.62)	17191.56 (10.98)	16366.70 (10.18)	16414.73 (10.98)
5	Manure	2887.50 (2.09)	5150.33 (3.29)	8275.43 (5.15)	4800.19 (3.21)
6	Fertilizer				
	N	648.37 (0.46)	722.16 (0.46)	534.15 (0.33)	638.26 (0.42)
	P	1143.32 (0.82)	1108.88 (0.70)	1161.65 (0.72)	1139.29 (0.76)
	K	567.70(0.41)	911.50 (0.58)	875.66 (0.54)	730.64 (0.48)
7	Irrigation	13900.12 (10.06)	14733.33 (9.41)	14900.76 (9.27)	14358.58 (9.61)
8	Plant Protection	7475.34 (5.41)	5716.62 (3.65)	6966.66 (4.33)	6908.49 (4.62)
9	Incidental Charges	197.50(0.14)	170.83 (0.10)	237.50 (0.14)	200.83 (0.13)
10	Repairing Charges	18 8.75 (0.13)	176.66 (0.11)	185.83 (0.11)	184.98 (0.12)
11	Working Capital	74987.12 (54.31)	86548.33 (55.31)	91437.50 (56.90)	79556.20 (53.63)
12	Interest On Working Capital @6 per cent	2249.61 (1.62)	2596.45 (1.65)	2584.31 (1.60)	2419.98 (1.63)
13	Miscellaneous Charges	192.50 (0.13)	175.83 (0.11)	233.33 (0.14)	196.04 (0.13)
14	Depreciation	877.18 (0.63)	784.23 (0.50)	1050.66 (0.65)	897.31 (0.60)
15	Land Revenue	191.25 (0.13)	176.66 (0.11)	203.33 (0.12)	190.62 (0.12)
16	COST "A1"	78055.48 (56.53)	89688.11 (57.31)	89913.06 (55.95)	83928.03 (56.58)
17	Rental Value of land	32869.16 (23.80)	38638.61 (24.69)	40842.50 (25.41)	36304.85 (24.47)
18	COST "A2"	78055.48 (56.53)	89688.11 (57.31)	89913.06 (55.95)	83928.03 (56.58)
19	Interest on fixed Capital @10%	4283.75 (3.10)	3192.5 (2.04)	3165.83 (1.97)	3731.45 (2.51)
20	COST B1	82339.23 (59.64)	92880.61 (59.35)	93078.89 (57.92)	87659.49 (59.10)
21	COST B2	115208.40 (83.44)	131519.22 (84.04)	133921.39 (83.34)	123964.36 (83.57)
22	Family Human Labour				
	Male	10725.26 (7.76)	11475.13 (7.33)	9512.57 (5.92)	10609.55 (7.15)
	Female	10300.15 (7.32)	10733.30 (6.85)	12150.08 (7.56)	10870.80 (7.32)
23	COST "C1"	103364.23 (74.86)	115088.95 (73.54)	114741.39 (71.41)	109139.70 (73.58)
24	COST "C2"	125508.40 (90.90)	142252.56 (90.90)	146071.39 (90.90)	134835.19 (90.90)
25	10% of COST "C2"	12550.84 (9.09)	14225.25 (9.09)	14607.13 (9.09)	13483.51 (9.09)
26	COST C3	138059.24 (100)	156477.81 (100)	160678.53 (100)	148319.02 (100)
27	Gross Income	198362.50	232891.66	246275.18	218972.96
28	B.C Ratio	1.44	1.48	1.51	1.47

(Figures in parentheses indicate the percentages to cost 'C₃')

Per hectare cost and returns of Brinjal

It is revealed from Table 3 that the overall average gross return worked out to Rs.218972.96 The net return obtained at various costs was Rs 135044.90 at cost 'A₂', Rs. 96756.32 at cost 'B₂', Rs 70654.20

at cost 'C₃' This means brinjal crop appeared to be good form monitory benefits. The highest input output ratio at cost 'C₃' was recorded in large size group, i.e., 1.51 and lowest input output ratio at cost 'C₃' was recorded small size group i.e., 1.44.

Table 3: Per hectare cost and returns of Brinjal

Sr No.	Particulars	Size group			
		Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Yield (Qtl.)	99.88	106.08	121.92	106.94
2	Value Main Produce(Rs)	198362.50	232891.66	246275.18	218972.96
3	Gross returns (Rs)	198362.50	232891.66	246275.18	218972.96
4	Total Cost (Rs)				
	Cost A1	78055.48	89688.11	89913.06	83928.03
	Cost A2	78055.48	89688.11	89913.06	83928.03
	Cost B1	82339.23	92880.61	93078.89	87659.49
	Cost B2	115208.40	131519.22	133921.39	123964.36
	Cost C1	103364.23	115088.95	114741.39	109139.70
	Cost C2	125508.40	142252.56	146071.39	134835.19
	Cost C3	138059.24	156477.81	160678.53	148319.02
5	Net Return Over (Rs)				
	Cost A1	120307.07	143203.55	156361.93	135044.90
	Cost A2	120307.07	143203.55	156361.93	135044.90
	Cost B1	116023.26	140011.05	153196.10	131313.41
	Cost B2	86649.63	101372.43	112353.60	96756.32
	Cost C1	94998.26	117802.71	131533.60	109833.21
	Cost C2	72854.09	90639.10	100203.60	84137.72
	Cost C3	60303.25	76413.84	85596.46	70654.20
6	Input Output ratio at				
	Cost A1	2.56	2.59	2.75	2.62
	Cost A2	2.56	2.59	2.75	2.62
	Cost B1	2.43	2.50	2.66	2.51
	Cost B2	1.81	1.76	1.82	1.80
	Cost C1	1.94	2.03	2.16	2.02
	Cost C2	1.58	1.63	1.67	1.61
	Cost C3	1.44	1.48	1.51	1.47

At the overall level the input output ratio at cost 'C₃' was 1.47. The input output ratio, which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and other discussion indicated that brinjal registered a good input output ratio 1.47, means this is profitable crop, hence hypothesis is accepted.

Technical and Economic efficiency of Brinjal

The results of the stochastic frontier production function estimates for the brinjal crop are shown in Table 4. The coefficient of area (1.01), higher labour (0.76), and fertilizer (0.04) were positive and statistically significant; hence, if the area, higher labour and fertilizer under cultivation increased by one per cent, it could increase the production by 1.01, 0.76 and 0.04 per cent, respectively. The coefficient of cost of seed (-0.67) and irrigation (-0.03) showed a significant negative effect on the yield. The results of the stochastic

frontier production function estimates for the tomato crop are shown in Table 4. The coefficient of area (0.09), higher labour (0.26), seeds (0.15) and irrigation (0.16) are showing positive effect on yield; hence, there scope for increasing these inputs in tomato cultivation in the study area. The coefficient of fertilizer shows positive and significant at one per cent level.

The results of the stochastic frontier production function estimates for chilli crop are shown in Table 4. The coefficient of area (0.49), higher labour (0.18), fertilizer (0.29) and irrigation (0.047) are showing positive and significant effect on yield. The coefficient of seeds shows negative and significant at one per cent level; hence, the negative elasticity of production of variables indicates excessive use of these inputs, which increase in further quantity decreases the yield.

Table 4: Estimation of technical and economic efficiency of brinjal by using stochastic frontier production function

Parameters	Technical Efficiency	Economic Efficiency
Intercept	0.25438 (0.00019)	3.16566 (0.00191)
Area (X1)	1.01363*** (0.00022)	0.71397*** (0.00188)
Hired labour (X2)	0.76282*** (0.00015)	0.47341*** (0.00071)
Seed (X3)	-0.67347*** (0.00024)	-1.02468*** (0.00066)
Fertilizer (X4)	0.04216*** (0.00028)	0.64859*** (0.0005)
Irrigation (X5)	-0.03708*** (0.00048)	-0.2805*** (0.00166)
Sigma-squared	0.01067	0.08047
Gamma	1.00	1.00

Log-likelihood	61.76	21.36
----------------	-------	-------

(***,**, * Indicate significance at 1,5, and 10 per cent level respectively)

It could be seen from Table 4 that, the brinjal that the coefficient of area (0.71), higher labour (0.47) and fertilizer (0.64) showed positive and significant increase effect on the profits at one per cent level; it could increase the production by 0.72, 0.47 and 0.64 per cent respectively. The coefficient of seed (-1.02) and irrigation (-0.28) showed a significant negative effect on the profits. It could be seen from Table 4 for the tomato that the area (-0.76) negative significant at ten per cent level. The coefficient of higher labour (-0.14) negative and fertilizer positive at ten per cent level. The coefficient of seed (0.14) and irrigation (0.44) positive; hence there scope for increasing these inputs in tomato cultivation in the study area.

The results of the stochastic frontier profit function estimates for chilli crop are shown Table 4 the coefficient of area (0.29), seed (0.21), fertilizer (0.66) and irrigation (0.21) are positive and

Table 5 Distribution of sample farmers under different levels of technical efficiency, economic efficiency and allocative efficiency in brinjal

Efficiency score	Technical efficiency		Economic efficiency		Allocative efficiency	
	Frequency	Percentage to total	Frequency	Percentage to total	Frequency	Percentage to total
<10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10.01-20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
20.01-30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
30.01-40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
40.01-50	0.00	0.00	1.00	2.50	0.00	0.00
50.01-60	0.00	0.00	1.00	2.50	1.00	2.50
60.01-70	0.00	0.00	4.00	10.00	2.00	5.00
70.01-80	2.00	5.00	11.00	27.50	5.00	12.50
80.01-90	9.00	22.50	12.00	30.00	16.00	40.00
>90	29.00	72.50	11.00	27.50	16.00	40.00
Total	40.00	100	40.00	100	40.00	100
Mean TE (%)	92.88		81.52		87.43	
Min TE (%)	76.82		43.41		56.51	
Max TE (%)	99.99		99.99		110.07	

The mean level of technical efficiency, economic efficiency and allocative efficiency has been estimated at 92.88 per cent, 81.52 per cent, and 87.43 per cent in brinjal cultivation.

Constraints in production and marketing of selected rabi vegetables.

Table 6 Constraints in production and marketing of selected vegetables

Sr. No	Problems	Score	Rank
A.	Constraints in Production		
1	High cost of fertilizer and other input.	61.23	I
2	High wage rate.	57.60	III
3	Infestation of insect and pest.	60.57	II
4	Lack of Financial Facility.	48.41	IV
5	Poor source of irrigation.	42.05	V
6	Non availability of storage facility.	32.35	VII
7	High cost of pesticide.	36.90	VI
B.	Constraints in Marketing		
1.	Delay in Sale and payment.	49.19	I
2.	High Transportation charges.	48.58	II
3.	High commission charges.	48.40	III
4.	Involvement of large number of intermediaries.	47.57	IV

The information regarding the significant issues faced by the growers is presented in Table 6. Brinjal growers were questioned about the challenges they face in growing and marketing of brinjal. The farmers

are analysed with the Garrett's ranking technique, and the overall results are shown in the following table. The farmers face a variety of issues, such as high cost of fertilizer and other inputs, infestation of

significant increase effect on profits; hence the area, seed, fertilizer and irrigation under cultivation increases by one per cent, it could increase the production by 0.29, 0.21, 0.66 and 0.21 per cent, respectively. The coefficient of higher labour (-0.94) negative significant at one per cent level.

Distribution of farmers under different level of production efficiencies

The technical and allocative efficiency scores of brinjal growers were calculated and are shown in Table 5. According to the brinjal grower frequency of technical efficiency score, 2 growers have efficiency between 70.01 and 80.01, 9 have efficiency between 80.01 and 90, and 29 have efficiency greater than 90. One of the brinjal growers had an allocative efficiency score between 50.01-60, according to the frequency analysis.

insect and pest, poor sources of irrigation. High cost of fertilizer it was expressed by 61.23 per cent of selected growers. The high cost of labour was the major problem, which was expressed by 57.60 per cent farmers, as this can affect timely cultivation and harvesting. Nonavailability of storage facility, Infestation of insect pests, poor source of irrigation, high cost of pesticide which was expressed by 32.35 per cent, 60.57 per cent, 42.05 per cent, 36.90 per cent. In regarding to marketing of selected vegetables, the high transportation charges by farmer were expressed by 48.58 per cent. Other marketing problems faced by farmers were delay in sale payment, high commission charges and involvement of large number of intermediaries expressed by 49.19 per cent, 48.40 per cent, 47.57 per cent, respectively.

Conclusions:

It is concluded from the present study that, the the Per hectare cost of cultivation at cost C₃ of brinjal, tomato and chilli were Rs. 148319.02, Rs. 160100.79 and Rs. 140719.62, respectively. The input-output ratio at cost C₃ for brinjal, tomato and chilli growers were 1.47, 1.44 and 1.29, respectively. The mean level of technical efficiency, economic efficiency and allocative efficiency has been estimated at 92.88 per cent, 81.52 per cent and 87.43 per cent in brinjal cultivation. In tomato cultivation, it has been estimated at 96.81 per cent, 90.79 per cent, and 91.13 per cent. And in chilli cultivation, it has been estimated at 93.91 per cent, 81.96 per cent and 86.98 per cent, respectively.

References:

1. **Adawadkar M. P.1*, Deshmukh M. M. 2, Wadatkar S. B.**3response Of Brinjal To Different Fertilizer Levels Under Drip Fertigation On Yield And Water Use Efficiency. Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxv, Jan 2023 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, 482-486
2. **Kumar, S.C., Pramanik, and Nawaz Shakila, 2004.** Economics of production and marketing of vegetables in Andaman and Nicobar Islands, Indian J Agril Mktg, 18(2): 16-22.
3. **Gal Chetan1, M. M. Pandya2*, N. A. Patel2, Rutvik J. Joshi1 and Bhavya Desai 2023,** "Illuminating The Genetic

4. **Goyal, M., & Singh, A. 2012.** Production and marketing related problems of vegetable growers in Punjab. *Indian Journal of Economics and Development*, 8(1), 63-70.
5. **Kumar, A. J., A.Y Yadav Sumita, M. K & A.K Rohila 2019.** Constraints faced by the farmers in production and marketing of vegetables in Haryana. *Indian journal of agricultural sciences*, 89(1), 153-60.
6. **Kumar, B.G., S.C Pramanik & S. Nawaz, 2004.** Economics of production and marketing of vegetables in Andaman and Nicobar Islands. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Marketing*, 18(2), 16-22.
7. **Nishant V. Shende and Mangal P. Tambe, 2021,** Economic Analysis Of Pesticide Use In Brinjal Cultivation, Vol. X, Issue Xxxvi, January 2021 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Pp 1515-1518.
8. **P. J. Gedam, S. M. Sarap, S.N. Ingle,2023,** Economics Of Production Of Brinjal In Nagpur District, Vol. Xiii, Issue Xxxvi, April 2023 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Pp 680-682.
9. **Shende, N. V. and Meshram, R.R. (2015).** Cost benefit analysis and marketing of tomato "*American International Journal of Research in Formal, Applied & Natural Sciences*" 11(1), 46-54.
10. **Tadavi, H., & H.R Shinde, 2021.** Cost, returns and resource use efficiency in Jalgaon brinjal production in Jalgaon district of Maharashtra. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 229-235.
11. **Tsoho, B. A., O.A Omotesho, S.A Salau, & M.O Adewumi, 2012.** Determinants of technical, allocative and economic efficiencies among dry season vegetable farmers in Sokoto state, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 3(2), 113-119.